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Toxicological Risk of Exposure to Hand-Dug Wells (HDWs): Physicochemical Quality and Elemental Level

**O. D. Umoren^{1,*}, S. T. Olowo², S. A. Dauda³, P. O. Abimbola⁴, I. H. Oseh⁵,
C. Ebite⁶, B. M. Ayorinde⁷ and O. O. Ajulo⁸**

¹ Department of Biological Sciences, National Open University of Nigeria, Abuja, Nigeria

² Department of Chemistry, University of Abuja, Abuja, Nigeria

³ Department of Energy Economics, Management and Policy, University of Port Harcourt, Nigeria

⁴ Department of Chemistry, University of Lagos, Akoka, Nigeria

⁵ Department of Chemistry, University of Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria

⁶ Department of Chemistry, Clemson University, Clemson, SC, United State

⁷ Department of Environmental Biology, University of Lagos, Akoka, Nigeria

⁸ Department of Geosciences, Fort Hays State University, Kansas, United State

*E-mail address: Otohifedayo@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Ensuring access to safe drinking water remains a critical challenge in developing regions, particularly in areas reliant on hand-dug wells. This study evaluates the physicochemical characteristics, trace element concentrations, and associated non-carcinogenic health risks of water samples from hand-dug wells (HDWs) in selected Areas in Abeokuta South Local Government Area (LGA), Ogun State, Nigeria. Water samples were collected from seven key areas within the LGA. Physicochemical parameters were analyzed using standard methods, while trace element levels were quantified via Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometry (AAS). The finding showed a range in temperature (24.6 – 25.2 °C), pH (5.8 – 6.8); electrical conductivity (0.852 – 1.36 μ S/cm), turbidity (0.4-3.0 NTU), Salinity (0.43 – 0.64 ppm), total dissolved solids (TDS)(76 – 909 mg/L), Total Acidity (20 – 66mg/L), total hardness (112 – 284 mg/L), chloride ion (74 – 134 mg/L), nitrate ion (3.0 – 43.6 mg/L), phosphate ion (0.22 – 4.93 mg/L), sulphate ion (22 – 95 mg/L) and dissolved oxygen (DO) (0 – 1.67 mg/L). Total dissolved

solid (TDS), TH and Nitrate ions in 71.4, 100 and 85.7% of the HDW respectively were above the WHO standards (<500, 100 and 5.0 mg/L). The Fe, Mn, Ag, Na and Zn levels are 0.89, 0.429, 0.006, 9.63 and 0.365 mg/L respectively. The levels of Cd and Ni were not detected or below the detectable limits across the HDWs. Toxic elements such as Mn and Ag are high in all the hand-dug wells and Kuto respectively compared to the WHO standard. Toxicological risk assessment indicated that the HI <1, suggesting that the people making use of the HDW are at a non-significant non-cancer risk on exposure. In conclusion, the study highlights the urgent need for water treatment interventions to ensure the safety and acceptability of water usage from the hand-dug wells.

Keywords: Human Health Risk, Hand Dug Well, physicochemical Quality, trace element

1. INTRODUCTION

Water is an essential tool for life on the earth's surface and is used for domestic, industrial and agricultural purposes. However, as the population of the world increases, there is a need for the supply of safe water so that a healthy life can be achieved (Elinge *et al.*, 2011; Famuyiwa *et al.*, 2025). Human activities have resulted in the contamination and pollution of nature, resulting in great degradation (Edori and Kpee, 2016a; Umoren *et al.*, 2024a). The proper use of water resources and their reach to man is a worldwide challenge, most especially in the continents of Africa (Halilu *et al.*, 2011; Osifeso *et al.*, 2025).

In Nigeria, due to the inability of the various authorities to provide water supply for its citizens, there has been a rise in the dependence on private hand-dug well water indiscriminately dug by individuals, corporate organizations and even government agencies in their different homes, and office environments (Edori and Kpee, 2016; Aluko *et al.*, 2024) to curb the menace of inadequate water supply. This alternative water supply is usually unmanaged, resulting in contamination of water sources (Umoren *et al.*, 2024c), contradicting the idea of sustainable development goals (Abii and Nwabienvanne, 2013).

Most natural water sources for human usage are mostly obtained underground and the restoration of contaminated groundwater to its original state is difficult and expensive (Belkhiri *et al.*, 2018). Pollutants such as toxic elements are introduced into groundwater (hand-dug well) even though they exist naturally underground. Toxic elements are well-known subterranean water contaminants, and they are one of the most significant pollutants influencing the underground water system (Aluko *et al.*, 2024). Toxic elements, also known as trace metals, have a high density and tend to build in any system that is not well monitored (Elinge *et al.*, 2011; Umoren *et al.*, 2024b).

Toxic elements are potentially harmful, and their toxicity is determined by the amount present in the environment (Famuyiwa *et al.*, 2023). Furthermore, when the capacity of the surface soil to retain toxic elements fails, they leach into the groundwater, where they can be exposed to humans and other living species (Edori *et al.*, 2016b).

Toxic elements can exist in particulate, dissolved and colloidal phases when found in water (Adepoju-Bello *et al.*, 2009). Toxic elements such as cadmium (Cd), arsenic (As), chromium (Cr), thallium (Tl), zinc (Zn), nickel (Ni), copper (Cu), and lead (Pb) have a relatively high density ranging from 3.5 to 7 g/cm³ and are dangerous or poisonous at low doses (Famuyiwa *et al.*, 2023).

The water supply in Abeokuta is not enough leading to the residents' dependence on alternative sources of water largely hand-dug wells (Umoren *et al.*, 2024d), Since water is of necessity for biological life, Hence, there is a need to assess the water quality of the hand dug wells to provide guidelines for their sustainable usage and/or implement corrective measures to ensure their quality. This study aims to evaluate the physicochemical characteristics, trace element concentrations, and associated non-carcinogenic health risks of water samples from hand-dug wells (HDWs) in selected Areas in Abeokuta South Local Government Area (LGA), Ogun State, Nigeria.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2. 1. Study Area

The study was carried out in Abeokuta South, Ogun State, Nigeria in February 2023. Abeokuta is located between latitude 7°20' north of the equator and between longitude 3°20' east of the Greenwich Meridian. Abeokuta is situated above a basement complex of volcanic rocks covered in some sedimentary strata. The city experiences the wet and dry seasons which run from April through October and November through March respectively (Umoren *et al.*, 2024c).

Table 1. Geographical description of study location

Sample	Locations	Coordinates
HW01	Isale Ake	7°09'54.3"N 3°21'26.0"E
HW02	Oke- Ejigbo	7°09'31.2"N 3°21'25.2"E
HW03	Adatan	7°10'07.3"N 3°21'32.6"E
HW04	Kuto	7°08'15.3"N 3°21'26.1"E
HW05	Oke-Ijeun	7°09'10.9"N 3°21'06.7"E
HW06	Isabo	7°08'51.0"N 3°20'56.5"E
HW07	Nawarudeen	7°08'53.6"N 3°21'08.8"E

2. 2. Sample Collection

The water samples used for this study were randomly collected from hand-dug wells in seven major areas in Abeokuta South Local Government (LGA), Ogun State. The samples were collected in polyethylene bottles (2 L) which had been pre-treated, and thoroughly washed with distilled water.

The bottles were emptied and rinsed several times with the water to be collected and were partially filled with the water and vigorously shaken to note the odour. The sample bottles were tightly covered immediately after collection and the pH and temperature were taken. Then transported in ice to the laboratory for further processing.

2. 3. Physicochemical Analysis

The pH and temperature were determined and recorded immediately at the site. The Electrical conductivity (EC), Total Dissolved Solid (TDS) and salinity were determined in the laboratory using a digital water meter. The chloride was determined by the argentometric method, phosphate by the Vanadate-molybdate method, sulphate by the turbidimetry method and nitrate (NO₃) by the UV spectrophotometric method. The Total Solids (TS) were determined gravimetrically while Dissolved Oxygen (DO) was determined by using Winkler's Method (Umoren *et al.*, 2024).

2. 4. Digestion and Elemental Analysis

To prevent precipitation of toxic elements in the solution, the solution of TEs is so unstable especially in high pH, to prevent such a problem, 50 cm³ of the water sample was measured into an evaporating dish and 5 cm³ of concentrated HNO₃ was added to the solution of TEs. Nitric acid (HNO₃) is added to water samples for TE analysis during the sampling of water. The samples were digested using a digestion block in a fume cupboard until the solution was reduced to 5 – 6mls with a characteristic colourless, indicating complete digestion. Each digest was then allowed to cool and transferred to a 50 cm³ acid-washed volumetric flask and the volume was brought to the 50 cm³ mark with deionized water. The diluted digest was then filtered and kept in sample bottles ready for analysis. The level of each TE in the samples was determined using a Buck Scientific 205 Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer.

2. 5. Toxicological Risk Assessment

Toxicological risks of exposure to the hand-dug well water sample were evaluated via the ingestion and skin contact route according to the United States Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA) equation (Famuyiwa *et al.*, 2025; Osifeso *et al.*, 2025). The average daily intake (ADI) for TEs in the sample was calculated using equations 1 and 2.

$$ADI_{ing} = C \times \frac{IngR \times EF \times ED}{BW \times AT} \times 10^{-6} \quad Eqn. 1$$

$$ADI_{derm} = (C \times SA \times PC \times EF \times ED \times CF) / (BW \times AT) \quad Eqn. 2$$

where ADI_{ing} is the average daily intake through ingestion (kilogram/body weight) (Hadzi *et al.*, 2018). C is the concentration of toxic metals in drinking water (mg/L), IngR is the ingestion rate per unit time (L/day), ED is the exposure duration (years), which is equal to the life expectancy, EF is the exposure frequency (days/ year), BW is body weight (kg), and AT is the averaging time (ED x EF). For the conversion factor from years to days, 365 days was used.

The hand-dug wells assessed in this study are potential sources of drinking and domestic water for the local population, therefore water ingestion and dermal contact are assumed to be the main pathways for risk assessment (Hadzi *et al.*, 2018) and where ADI_{derm} is the average

daily intake via dermal exposure, Sa is the total skin surface area (cm²), CF is the volumetric conversion factor for water (1 L/1000 cm³), Et is the exposure duration (h/day), PC is the chemical-specific dermal permeability constant (cm/h), EF is the exposure frequency (days/years), ED is the exposure duration (years), and BW is body weight.

The non-cancer risk expressed as the hazard quotient (HQ) was calculated by dividing the ADI for elements on ingestion & dermal exposure pathways with their respective reference doses (RfDs) in mg/L/day using equation 3.

$$\text{Hazard Quotient (HQ)} = \text{ADI} / \text{RfD} \quad \text{Eqn. 3}$$

The hazard index was performed by summing the calculated hazard quotient (HQ) from each exposure route using Equation 4. The purpose of the hazard assessment is to evaluate whether an agent poses a non-cancer hazard to humans upon exposure (Naveedullah *et al.*, 2014).

$$\text{Hazard Index (HI)} = \sum \text{HQ}_i \quad \text{Eqn. 4}$$

where HQ represents the hazard quotient via ingestion or dermal contact and RfD is the oral/dermal reference dose (mg/L/day). Finally, the carcinogenic risks (CRs) of the elements were estimated using equation 4 to assess the probability of an individual developing cancer over a lifetime exposure to the well water sample. The slope factor (SF) is a toxicity value that quantitatively defines the relationship between dose and response. Potential carcinogenic effect probabilities that an individual will develop cancer over a lifetime of exposure are estimated from projected intakes and slope factors. The range for carcinogenic risk acceptable or tolerable stipulated by the USEPA is 1×10^{-6} to 1×10^{-4}

$$\text{Cancer Risk}_i = \text{ADI}_i \times \text{SF}_i \quad \text{Eqn. 5}$$

where CR_i represents the cancer risk due to ingestion and dermal exposure routes, respectively, and SF is the slope factor (mg/kg/ day).

2. 6. Data Analysis

Microsoft Excel 2013 version was used for data analysis, graphical presentation and also for computing health risk assessment.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3. 1. Physicochemical Qualities

Tables 2 show the physicochemical parameters of the water samples from each of the seven samples investigated. The pH values of the water ranged from about acidic to slightly neutral (5.8 – 6.8). pH values of all the hand-dug wells fall within the range of 6.5 to 8.5. The lowest pH was recorded in Kuto while the highest was recorded equally in Isale-Ake, Adatan, and Isabo. All pH was within the WHO standard (6.5-8.5). The pH values, which indicate the acidity and alkalinity of the sampled hand-dug well show that the ground waters are safe for

use. This is contrary to the previous results reported from the same areas (Ganiyu *et al.*, 2017), showing that all water is generally alkaline. According to Isa *et al.* (2013) and Umoren *et al.* (2024b), harm as a result of extreme pH in water samples was not recorded but an alteration in the normal human body physiology can emerge.

The hand-dug well water temperatures ranged from 24.6 - 25.2 °C. The lowest temperature was recorded in Adatan while the highest was recorded in Oke-Ejigbo. The temperatures recorded in 04/07 of the wells were slightly below the WHO standard (25.0-29.0 °C). Although there is seasonal variation in well water temperature levels, this could be related to climatic circumstances at a certain geographic area and time. The turbidity ranged between 0.4 - 3.0 NTU. The lowest turbidity was recorded in Kuto while the highest was recorded in Nawarudeen. All turbidity values were within the WHO standard (5 NTU). The water turbidity state is used to determine the transparency of the water, and the occurrence of turbidity can be a result of the increase in microbial population in the water source (Isa *et al.*, 2013).

The electrical conductivity (EC) of the water samples ranged from 0.852 - 1.36 mS/cm. The lowest EC was recorded in Isabo while the highest was recorded in Nawarudeen. The majority of hand-dug wells have EC values higher than the WHO standard (1.0 mS/cm) except for Isale Ake and Isabo. The EC of a water sample is a useful and easy indicator of its salinity or total salt content. The EC of water samples from the study was high, this is largely due to an elevated amount of inorganic dissolved solids in the water, which could emanate from different substances finding their way into this well water due to ignorance of improper care of the well (Aluko *et al.*, 2024). The salinity values of all the water sources ranged between 0.43 and 0.64 ppm. The lowest salinity was recorded in Isabo while the highest was recorded in Oke-Ijeun. All the hand-dug wells have a salinity within the WHO standard (100 ppm).

The total dissolved solids (TDS) and total solids (TS) ranged from 76 - 909 mg/L. The lowest TDS and TS were recorded in Nawarudeen while the highest was recorded in Oke-Ijeun respectively. All hand-dug wells have a TDS value except Nawarudeen was above the WHO standard (500 mg/L) while All the well samples had a TS value below the WHO standard (1500 mg/L). Some treatments such as the addition of coagulants may be required to make these waters suitable for domestic purposes. The high TDS detected from the majority of the well samples might have emanated from geogenic sources and sewage, High TDS in water does not cause harmful effects but may affect the taste of the well water (WHO, 2011). The TDS from the study is exponentially higher than the report from the KNUST campus, Ghana (51.96 mg/L) (Hayford and Appiah-Adjei, 2022).

Total acidity in the sample ranged from 20 - 66 mg/L. The lowest Total acidity was recorded in Oke-Ejigbo while the highest was recorded in Isabo. The total hardness ranged from 112 - 284 mg/L. The lowest total hardness was recorded in Nawarudeen while the highest was recorded in Oke-Ijeun. All the hand dug well have a total hardness above the WHO standard (100 mg/L). An elevated water hardness occurs as a result of the presence of alkaline earth metallic cations (Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+}) in water (WHO, 2011). The Total hardness reported from the hand-dug wells is higher than the report from the well in Kano (16.3 mg/L) by Abubakar and Sa'id (2022). The concentrations of Chloride ion (Cl^-) in the well water ranged between 74 - 134 mg/L. The lowest Cl^- was recorded in Isale-Ake while the highest was recorded in Nawarudeen. All the hand-dug wells have a Cl^- concentration within the WHO standard (250 mg/L).

The concentration of nitrate ion (NO_3^-) ranged between 3.0 43.6 mg/L. The lowest NO_3^- concentration was recorded in Kuto while the highest was recorded in Oke-Ejigbo. The majority

of the hand-dug well has NO₃ concentrations except for Kuto and Nawarudeen above the WHO standard (10 mg/L). The hand-dug well has a phosphate ion (PO₄) ranging from 0.22 and 4.93 mg/L. The lowest PO₄ concentration was recorded in Isabo while the highest was recorded in Isale-Ake. All the hand-dug wells have PO₄ concentrations within the WHO standard (5.0 mg/L). The concentration of sulphate ion (SO₄) ranged from 22 - 95 mg/L.

The lowest concentration of SO₄ was recorded in Nawarudeen while the highest was recorded in Oke-Ejigbo. All the hand-dug wells have SO₄ concentrations within the WHO standard (250 mg/L). The Dissolved Oxygen (DO) were found within the range of 0 to 1.67 mg/L.

Table 2. Physiochemical analysis of hand-dug well.

Parameter	Isale Ake	Oke-Ejigbo	Adatan	Kuto	Oke-ljeun	Isabo	Nawarudeen	Range	Mean ± SD	WHO Standard
Temperature @ 25 °C	25	25.2	24.6	25.2	24.9	24.9	24.9	24.6 – 25.2	24.9 ± 0.42	25.0 – 29.0°C
pH	6.8	6.6	6.8	5.8	6.6	6.8	6.7	5.8 – 6.8	6.3 ± 0.70	6.5 - 8.5
Turbidity	1.0	0.9	0.9	0.4	0.6	1.1	3.0	0.4 – 3.0	1.70 ± 1.83	5 NTU
Conductivity @ 25.2 °C	0.904	1.18	1.10	1.10	1.28	0.852	1.36	0.852 – 1.36	1.11 ± 0.36	1.0 mS/cm
Salinity @ 25.2 °C	0.48	0.59	0.55	0.55	0.64	0.43	0.52	0.43 – 0.64	0.54 ± 0.14	100 ppm
Total Dissolved Solids	677	837	782	779	909	607	76	76 – 909	492.5 ± 589.01	500 mg/L
Total Solid	677	837	782	779	909	607	76	76 – 909	492.5 ± 589.01	1500 mg/L
Total Acidity	58	20	32	30	54	66	32	20 – 66	43 ± 32.5	NS
Total Hardness	176	260	204	176	284	152	112	112 – 284	198 ± 121.62	100 mg/L
Chlorides	74	132	102	116	108	84	134	74 – 134	104 ± 42.42	250 mg/L
Nitrates	31.2	43.6	18.7	3.0	20.5	24.8	3.8	3.0 – 43.6	23.3 ± 28.70	10 mg/L
Phosphates	4.93	0.43	0.38	0.39	3.57	0.22	2.21	0.22 – 4.93	2.58 ± 3.33	5.00 mg/L
Sulphates	41	95	61	46	63	54	22	22 – 95	58.5 ± 51.61	250 mg/L
Dissolved Oxygen	Nd	Nd	1.23	Nd	0.26	Nd	1.67	0 – 1.67	1.67 ± 0.83	<2.0 mg/L

Keys: Nd = non detected; NS = not specified

The lowest DO was recorded in Oke-Ijeun while the highest was recorded in Nawarudeen. All the hand-dug wells have a DO value within the WHO standard (<2.0 mg/L). The low concentration of DO in the sample shows a reduced amount of living organisms in the water sample, since a reduced DO, cannot support the microbial reduction of nitrate to nitrite and sulfate to sulfide (Umoren *et al.*, 2024b)

3. 2. Element Level

Table 3 represents the concentrations of toxic elements in the hand-dug well water samples. The concentration of sodium (Na) in the samples are 0.781, 1.199, 0.994, 2.45, 1.2324, 0.991 and 1.99 mg/L for Isale Ake, Okejigbo, Adatan, Kuto, Oke – Ijeun, Isabo and Nawarudeen respectively. All the hand-dug wells were within the WHO standards (200 mg/L). The concentration of Mn recorded from the sample is 0.070, 0.051, 0.013, 0.104, 0.057, 0.077 and 0.058 mg/L for Isale Ake, Okejigbo, Adatan, Kuto, Oke – Ijeun, Isabo and Nawarudeen respectively. The majority of the hand-dug wells have a concentration above the WHO standards (0.05 mg/L). Exposure to high levels of manganese in drinking water can cause neurological and behavioural problems, especially in children (O’Neal & Zheng, 2015).

The levels of zinc (Zn) in the wells are 0.089, 0, 0.0415, 0.158, 0, 0.0433 and 0.0333 mg/L for Isale Ake, Okejigbo, Adatan, Kuto, Oke – Ijeun, Isabo and Nawarudeen respectively. The concentrations of Zn in all the hand-dug wells were within the WHO standards (3.0 mg/L). The concentration of iron (Fe) recorded from the sample are 0.015, 0.1368, 0.0792, 0.0464, 0.3211, 0.1121 and 0.175 mg/L for Isale Ake, Okejigbo, Adatan, Kuto, Oke – Ijeun, Isabo and Nawarudeen respectively. The concentrations of Fe in all the hand-dug wells were within the WHO standards (0.3 mg/L) for Fe in drinking water (WHO, 2011). The concentration of silver (Ag) from the well sample was only recorded in Kuto (0.006 mg/L) and above the WHO standard (0.005 mg/L). Silver intoxication can result in a condition in which silver is deposited on skin and hair, and in various organs (Famuyiwa *et al.*, 2025).

Table 3. Elemental Level (mg/L) in HDWs.

Elements (mg/L)	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	Mean	Std. Dev.	WHO
Cd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	-	-	0.003
Fe	0.015	0.137	0.079	0.046	0.321	0.112	0.175	0.886	0.101	0.3
Mn	0.070	0.051	0.013	0.104	0.057	0.077	0.058	0.429	0.028	0.05
Ni	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	-	-	0.02
Ag	nd	nd	nd	0.006	nd	nd	nd	0.006	0.002	0.005
Na	0.781	1.20	0.99	2.45	1.23	0.991	1.99	9.63	0.609	200
Zn	0.089	nd	0.042	0.158	nd	0.043	0.033	0.365	0.056	3.0

Keys: A = Isale Ake, B= Okejigbo, C = Adatan, D = Kuto, E = Oke – Ijeun, F = Isabo, G = Nawarudeen, nd = non detected

3. 3. Toxicological Risk Assessment

Toxic metals are mostly carcinogenic as they tend to accumulate in the visual and sensory organs of living organisms (Famuyiwa *et al.*, 2023; Umoren *et al.*, 2024b). The human health risk assessment of children and adults' exposure to the hand-dug well water shown in Tables 4 and 5, revealed that the children population are more exposed to the toxic element in the sampled well water than the adult population. More so, ingestion is mapped as the major route of exposure to both populations.

The exposure to TEs appears in the following order Na>Zn>Mn>Fe>Ag. Hazard Index (HI) is used to determine the non-cancer risk of the human population on exposure to well water.

The HI value becomes significant when the value is greater than 1, the HI value from the study visualized in Figures 3 and 4 revealed that the children and adult making uses of the well water are at a non-significant non –cancer risk, since all the values were less than 1.

The HI value appears in an order of Mn>Zn>Ag. The study TEs considered does not have a cancer slope factor, therefore the cancer risk of the TEs was not calculated.

Figures 3 & 4. Hazard Index for Children and Adults on exposure.

Table 4. Average daily intake (ADI)

Trace Element	Children			Adults		
	HQ _{ing}	HQ _{derm}	HI=∑HQ _i	HQ _{ing}	HQ _{derm}	HI=∑HQ _i
Zn	1.14E-05	3.20E-08	1.15E-05	1.23E-06	2.83E-08	1.26E-06
Mn	2.88E-05	8.07E-08	2.89E-05	3.09E-06	7.13E-08	3.16E-06
Ag	1.07E-05	-	-	1.14E-06	-	-

Table 5. Non-cancer risk

Trace Element	Children		Adults	
	ADI _{ing}	ADI _{derm}	ADI _{ing}	ADI _{derm}
Na	9.07E-05	2.54E-07	9.72E-06	2.25E-07
Zn	3.43E-06	9.61E-09	3.68E-07	8.50E-09
Mn	4.03E-06	1.13E-08	4.32E-07	9.98E-09
Fe	8.35E-06	2.34E-08	8.95E-07	2.07E-08
Ag	5.33E-08	1.49E-10	5.71E-09	1.32E-10

4. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The physicochemical, toxic elements and toxicological risks of selected hand-dug wells water from seven areas (Isale Ake, Okejigbo, Adatan, Kuto, Oke-Ijeun, Isabo and Nawarudeen) in Abeokuta, Ogun state, Nigeria were evaluated. The result shows high temperature in four, pH in one, EC & Nitrate in five, TDS in six, and Total hardness in all the hand dug well compared to the WHO threshold limit.

Toxic elements such as Mn and Ag are high in all the hand dug wells and Kuto respectively compared to the WHO threshold limit. Furthermore, toxicological risk assessment revealed that the children and adults making use of the hand-dug well water are at a non-significant non-cancer risk. Although the hand-dug well sample indicated no significant health problems, close monitoring of the hand-dug well water is essential if it is to be used as a source of drinking water to avoid an unpleasant taste.

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